

Does size play a role in induced displacement in magneto-motive ultrasound imaging?

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Abstract— *Over the past decade, a technique called magneto-motive ultrasound imaging (MMUS) has been established to obtain displacement of magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) due to the interaction between MNPs and the magnetic field. Recently, shear wave dispersion magneto-motive ultrasound imaging (SDMMUS), which is a subdivision of MMUS modality, has been introduced as a novel elasticity imaging to obtain viscoelastic properties of soft tissue mimicking phantoms labeled with iron oxide nanoparticles. In this technique, an alternating external magnetic field applied to induce displacements in order of micrometers and the mechanical properties of the medium resulted from these movements. Here, two different iron oxide MNPs synthesized by co-precipitation method, having the same saturation magnetizations but two different mean particle sizes were used as contrast agent in MMUS. Gelatin tissue mimicking phantoms were prepared containing inclusion with the MNPs to perform the experiments. According to the obtained results, the induced displacements were almost the same for both samples, suggesting in MNPs with the same magnetization and the mean size ranges studied here, the effect of size on the induced displacement can be neglected. Moreover, the mechanical properties of phantoms were reported the same values for both MNPs used.*

Keywords—*Magneto-motive ultrasound, shear wave, magnetic nanoparticles, mechanical properties.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Over few decades, elastography has been known as a well-known imaging modality due to mapping mechanical properties of tissues. Some diseases in different tissues including breast, liver, and so on have been recognized through changes of mechanical properties. Since the viscoelasticity of soft tissues is often associated with pathological state, they can be used as a diagnostic tool in medicine [1].

Ultrasound-based methods have been widely used compared to other techniques including magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), Single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT), and so forth due to many inherent advantages, including real time, cost effectiveness, portability and non-ionizing radiation [2]. However stand-alone ultrasound imaging has a poor contrast for magnetic nanoparticles.

Currently, magnetic nanoparticles have become a promising tool in the clinical diagnostic and therapeutic techniques as their capacity to function at the cellular and molecular level of

biological as well as their physical properties. MNPs in the form of superparamagnetic iron oxides (SPIO) have been established as a contrast enhancement for MRI imaging [3, 4]. However, as mentioned above, magnetic nanoparticles have shown weak contrast agents to ultrasound imaging. Therefore, a novel remote elastography called MMUS method has been introduced by oh et al. [5] to deal with this issue. MMUS is one of the recent modalities which benefits from superparamagnetic nanoparticle as contrast agent to visualize molecular and cellular levels through ultrasound imaging. In this technique, an external magnetic excitation is applied to induce a motion within tissue labeled with magnetic nanoparticles and this movement is detected by ultrasound technique [5]. Later, many researchers have been developing this modality to improve the sensitivity of ultrasound to detect magnetic nanoparticles. Mehrmohamadi et al.[6], Yaser et al. [7] and Evertsson et al [8] have enhanced signal to noise ratio (SNR) by different methods. Moreover, Mehrmohammadi et al. [9] used the MMUS modality to localize the motion of superparamagnetic nanoparticles with different concentration of Fe₃O₄ labeled in tissue mimicking PVA phantoms. MMUS has also been used to detect sentinel lymph nodes in rats [10]. Recently, in our group a new method called SDMMUS was developed by Pavan et al., 2012 [11]; Almeida et al., 2015 [12]. In this technique the viscoelastic parameters of the medium including shear elasticity (μ_1) and shear viscosity (μ_2) were obtained through tracking the propagation of shear wave. Moreover, later, another group Grasland-Mongrain et al.[13] created shear wave in soft tissues using the combination of a remotely induced electrical current and a magnetic field. The aim of this work was, to investigate the effect of size of MNPs on the induced displacements in MMUS. Here, we used two MNPs which has two different sizes 12.5 and 20 nm while their magnetization saturation was similar. We could observe this difference in the range of size did not effect on the induced displacement. Furthermore, the mechanical properties of soft tissue mimicking phantoms were shown almost the same values.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Phantom preparation

Our samples were gelatin based phantoms (Bovine gelatin, Bloom 250). Firstly, two different inclusions were prepared, in which they were labeled with 1 wt. % of superparamagnetic magnetic nanoparticles. Gelatin (4 wt. %)

was hydrated with a solution of deionized water at 25°C and heated to 70°C to obtain a homogeneous solution without trapped gases [14, 15]. Then, the solution was kept in room temperature until the temperature decrease to 50°C. Therefore, desired iron oxide nanoparticles with the size of 12.5 and 20 nm (magnetization 40 emu/g) [7] were mixed in the solution. Thereafter, 0.037 ml of formaldehyde was added in the temperature of 40 ° C. Formaldehyde is used to increase the melting point and elastic Modulus [14]. While the solution is in liquid state, the mixture was poured into a cylinder mold with diameter and height of 20 mm and was attached to a motorized system in order to maintain uniform distribution of nanoparticles. Then, sample was rested inside a refrigerator at 5°C for 24 h. The next procedure was manufacturing background phantom (60 mm in diameter and height) which was consisted of 2 wt. % agar and 4 wt. % gelatin. All of the steps were the same as aforementioned procedure for preparing inclusion, but here gelatin mixed with agar Bacteriologic CAT. RM026 was supplied by HIMEDIA). Here, the solution was heated until reach 90° C to get homogeneous. This mixture also was maintained in room temperature to reach 35 °C and then poured into a cylinder mold where the inclusion was positioned in the bottom of it. Finally, the phantom was maintained inside of the refrigerator again for 24 more hours. The samples were made by the same procedures 4 wt. % and 2 wt. % gelatin and agar respectively.

B. Experimental setup

According to studies [5, 7, 9] considering external magnetic field with a flux density of B in z direction and angular frequency of ω_0 , the one dimensional magnetic force $F(z)$ acting on a magnetic nanoparticle can be described as:

$$F(z) = \chi_{np} V_{np} / 2 \mu_0 (1 - \cos(2\omega_0 t)) B_z(z) \partial B_z(z) / \partial z \quad (1)$$

where μ_0 is permeability of free space, χ_{np} is the magnetic susceptibility of nanoparticles, V_{np} is the total volume of nanoparticles. This equation shows that the force is linearly proportional to the magnetic susceptibility of the nanoparticles as well as the magnitude and the gradient of magnetic flux density. It should also be noted that the oscillation frequency of the nanoparticles, due to this force, is two times larger than the excitation frequency [9].

A Schematic depiction of the setup for MMUS experiments is depicted in Fig.1. 10 cycles of sinusoidal voltage with different range of frequencies from 50 to 250 Hz were applied to a coil to create the excitation magnetic field. The coil (Solen Inc., Saint-Hubert, QC, Canada) has inner and outer diameters of 45 mm and 89 mm respectively, and height of 22 mm. A ferrite core of 1 cm diameter was inserted in the center of the coil to focus on a small area of the phantom. The coil was driven by a function generator (Agilent, model 33522A) connected to a power amplifier (Ciclotron, model Dynamic 20000 Ω , class H). A linear ultrasound transducer (model LA14-5/38) operating at a central frequency of 9.5 MHz connected to an ultrasound system (SONIX RP, Ultrasonix) with 128 piezoelectric elements and 5 to 14 MHz bandwidth was used. The echo signals were acquired using an ultrasound by applying a frame rate of 2 kHz. After acquiring all data, the induced displacements are tracked through normalized cross-correlating algorithm [16, 17]. The velocity of shear wave was assessed by tracking the peaks of maximum displacements during its propagation through depth using a time to peak (TTP) algorithm [17].

Fig. 1. Schematic depiction of the experimental setup for MMUS experiments.

C. VISCOELASTICITY MODEL

According to some studies [18, 19] the Kelvin-Voigt model has been known as an optimized model to estimate shear elasticity and shear viscosity of soft tissue mimicking phantoms. There is a relationship between the SW velocity and the viscoelastic properties of an isotropic homogeneous medium which discussed by Chen et al.[20] that we used this model as well. Here, the algorithm of Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm [21] was used to obtain viscoelastic properties by using a non-linear fitting.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Shear wave propagation after the induced displacement at 100 Hz, was shown in Fig. 2 (a) and fig. 2 (b) for phantoms including MNPs with size 12.5 and 20 nm, respectively. Based on the obtained results, although MNPs used had differences in sizes due to having the same magnetization, the induced displacement (according to the color bar) was almost equal for both samples at around 35 μm . Fig. 3 reports the shear wave velocity in five different frequencies obtained with SDMMUS. As can be observed, the mechanical properties of the samples were illustrated almost the same value of shear elasticity and viscosity. The acquired values of shear elasticity were 2.08 ± 0.33 and 1.76 ± 0.26 kPa for MNPs (20 nm) and (12.5 nm), respectively. The shear viscosities were 1.08 ± 0.19 and 1.034 ± 0.14 Pa.s, respectively. Hence, based on the observed results in this study using MNPs with the same magnetization but small differences in the sizes, did not effect on the induced displacements in MMUS. However, to have a better insight more MNPs should be used with larger differences in sizes.

Fig.2. The SW propagating through the soft-tissue-mimicking phantom at 100 Hz for MNPs with size 12.5 nm (a) and 20 nm (b), respectively.

Fig.3. The velocity of SW for SDMMUS. These data were fitted to the Voigt model to obtain shear elasticity and shear viscosity.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, we investigated using MNPs that have same magnetization but small differences in size (the maximum size used was 20 nm) did not effect on the induced displacement in MMUS. However, more studies should be investigated by applying MNPs with higher mean sizes as well as comparing bigger differences in the sizes. The viscoelastic parameters of the phantoms were calculated by applying the Voigt model and Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm. Shear elasticity and shear viscosity of two MNPs showed near similar values.

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